

“DESIGN AND FABRICATION OF GRAIN DRYER”

Darshan Reddy T C¹, Murtuj Kandagal¹, Niteesh V H¹, Ranjith M A¹,
Arunkumar H^{*2}

¹UG Scholars, School of Mechanical Engineering, REVA University,

^{*2}Assistant Professor, School of Mechanical Engineering, REVA University.

ABSTRACT

This project aims to revolutionize grain processing through the development of an advanced grain dryer system, integrating drying and cleaning functionalities for enhanced efficiency, sustainability, and cost-effectiveness in agriculture. It employs a hybrid energy source, combining renewable (solar) and conventional energy, to optimize efficiency and mitigate operational costs. The system aims for unparalleled efficiency without compromising cost-effectiveness, setting new standards for operational excellence. Emphasizing accessibility and scalability, particularly for small-scale farmers, it prioritizes a compact footprint and user-friendly design. By integrating solar energy sources, such as for the air blowing fan, the project reduces carbon emissions and promotes eco-friendly practices in grain processing, contributing to the long-term sustainability of agricultural production systems.

Keywords— Grain dryer, Grain cleaner, hybrid energy

I. Introduction

1.1 Grain Dryer:

In the bustling world of agriculture, where fields stretch to the horizon and the promise of harvest looms large, grain drying stands as a vital process in ensuring the quality and longevity of harvested crops. As grains are gathered from the fields, they carry with them a significant amount of moisture, making them susceptible to spoilage if not properly dried and stored. This is where grain dryer systems come into play—a cornerstone of post-harvest handling that facilitates the drying of grains to safe moisture levels, preserving their nutritional value and preventing mold and bacterial growth.

At its essence, a grain dryer system is a sophisticated piece of equipment designed to remove moisture from freshly harvested grains, ensuring their suitability for storage and subsequent processing. While the concept of grain drying may seem straightforward, the implementation of an efficient and effective drying process requires careful consideration of various factors, including temperature, airflow, and humidity levels.

The fundamental objective of a grain dryer system is to create an optimal drying environment that accelerates the evaporation of moisture from the grains while minimizing the risk of damage or over-drying. Traditionally, grain dryer systems have relied on heat generated by fossil fuels such as natural gas or propane to facilitate the drying process. However, advancements in technology and growing concerns about energy consumption and environmental sustainability have spurred the development of more innovative and eco-friendly drying solutions.

Fig. no.1 (Grain Dryer Machine)

Beyond their role in moisture removal, modern grain dryer systems often incorporate additional functionalities, such as cleaning and sorting, to further enhance grain quality and value. These multifunctional systems streamline the post-harvest handling process, enabling farmers to efficiently prepare their grains for storage, transport, and market sale.

As the demand for efficient and sustainable grain drying solutions continues to rise, the development of innovative grain dryer systems remains a focal point of agricultural research and technology. With each advancement, these systems play a crucial role in supporting food security, preserving crop quality, and promoting environmental stewardship in agricultural communities around the world.

1.2 Grain Cleaner:

In the world of farming and agriculture, after harvesting grains like wheat, rice, or corn, they need to go through a special process called grain cleaning. This process is like giving the grains a bath to remove any dirt, dust, or other unwanted bits they may have picked up in the field. Grain cleaners are the superheroes of this process, helping to ensure that the grains we eat are clean, safe, and ready for use

A grain cleaner is a machine designed specifically to remove impurities from grains, making them suitable for consumption or further processing. Think of it as a giant sieve or filter that separates the good stuff (the grains) from the bad stuff (dust, debris, and other unwanted materials).

The process of grain cleaning typically involves passing the grains through a series of screens, sieves, and air streams that help to separate out the impurities based on size, weight, and density. By carefully controlling the flow of grains and adjusting the settings of the machine, farmers can effectively remove unwanted materials while retaining the quality and integrity of the grains.

Fig. no. 2 (Grain Cleaning Machine)

Grain cleaners come in various shapes and sizes, from small, portable units suitable for small-scale farmers to large, industrial-grade machines used in commercial grain processing facilities.

Regardless of size, the goal remains the same: to ensure that the grains are clean, safe, and free from contaminants before they are stored, sold, or processed into food products.

In addition to improving food safety and quality, grain cleaners also play a crucial role in maximizing the value of harvested grains. By removing impurities and foreign materials, farmers can sell their grains at higher prices and avoid costly rejections or discounts from buyers. This makes grain cleaners not only essential tools for ensuring food safety but also valuable investments for farmers looking to optimize their profits.

Overall, grain cleaners are indispensable machines in the agricultural industry, helping to ensure the cleanliness, safety, and quality of the grains that nourish communities around the world. As the demand for safe and sustainable food continues to grow, the importance of grain cleaners in ensuring food security and quality remains as vital as ever.

1.3 Combination of Grain Dryer and Cleaner:

For a long time, to proceed with the cleaning and drying process of the cereals separate equipment was used: they proceeded at different times to complete the processes of cleaning and drying. However, this implies a greater waste of time as well as a higher cost, for the purchase of two different machines and for the maintenance. Furthermore, as can be easily understood, two machines also require a larger space, which can make the corporate layout less functional. Today the most advanced solutions provide for cleaning and drying cereals with a single machine. This is possible thanks to the integration of the basic dryer for cleaning the product. The cleaner is mounted on the dryer and adjusted to extract the thinnest parts and also the grains extraneous to the product to dry. Combining the cleaning phase within the drying phase it is possible not only with fixed systems, such as tower dryers, but also with portable and smaller ones, such as mobile grain dryers.

Fig no. 3 (Design and Drafting of model)

2. LITERATURE

The literature on grain dryer systems presents a diverse array of innovative approaches aimed at improving energy efficiency, reducing emissions, and maintaining grain quality. Wang et al. introduce the 5HLN-R-50 electric grain dryer, which incorporates internal circulation to achieve zero emissions and a remarkable 48% energy savings compared to Chinese standards. This system, powered by clean electric energy, utilizes controlled condensation to ensure consistent grain quality, making it an environmentally friendly solution for grain drying.

Jimoh et al. delve into the significance of drying kinetics in preserving grain quality and consumer acceptance. Their study explores a combination of drying technologies such as microwave, infrared, and fluidized bed dryers, along with treatments like ultrasound and dehumidification. By evaluating various drying methods, including convective hot air and hybrid dryers, they emphasize substantial improvements in energy efficiency, with microwave and infrared methods showing energy savings of up to 84% and 67%, respectively, compared to conventional hot air drying.

Yan et al. focus on enhancing the efficiency of drying freshly harvested peanuts through a modified mixed-flow dryer. Their research highlights specific energy and heat consumption, as well as the fluctuation of efficiencies with airflow temperature. They identify three drying stages and demonstrate a tripling of energy efficiency compared to thermal efficiency, emphasizing the potential for improved energy utilization in grain drying processes.

Chojnacka et al. address the challenge of reducing drying costs through effective energy management. They review recent innovations in seed and grain drying systems, particularly focusing on hybrid methods such as microwave-assisted, infrared-assisted, and ultrasound-assisted techniques. These approaches have shown promising results, reducing non-renewable energy consumption by up to 80% while also discussing exhaust gas purification techniques and the integration of renewable energy sources to minimize environmental impact.

Dissanayak et al. present the development of a mobile dryer designed for freshly harvested paddy, aiming to mitigate moisture-related issues during processing. Their one-ton capacity dryer demonstrates high thermal efficiency and efficient heat utilization despite initial challenges, making it suitable for hire basis paddy drying. With a reasonable drying time and cost, this mobile dryer offers a practical solution for small-scale paddy processing operations.

Pablos proposes a model for predicting the performance of spouted bed dryers, focusing on heat and mass transfer coefficients in fountain confined conical spouted beds.

2.1 METHODOLOGY

Fig no. 4 (Methodology)

Initial Research and Analysis: Conduct a comprehensive review of existing grain dryer systems and technologies to identify strengths, weaknesses, and opportunities for improvement. Analyse market trends, customer needs, and regulatory requirements to inform the design and development process.

Conceptualization and Design Phase: Brainstorm and generate concepts for the grain dryer system, considering integration of drying and cleaning functionalities. Develop preliminary design sketches and specifications based on research findings and identified objectives.

Energy Source Integration: Explore the integration of hybrid energy sources, including renewable (e.g., solar) and conventional (e.g., electricity) energy sources.

Assess the feasibility and effectiveness of incorporating solar panels to harness solar energy for powering components of the grain dryer system.

Component Selection and Procurement: Identify and select appropriate components for the grain dryer system, including conveyors, heater, air blowing fan, and energy sources. Procure necessary materials and equipment from reliable suppliers, ensuring compatibility and quality standards are met.

Fabrication: Fabrication of the grain dryer system based on the finalized design specifications. Assemble components and subsystems according to design plans, ensuring proper alignment and functionality. Conduct preliminary testing to evaluate the performance and functionality of the prototype under controlled conditions.

Testing and Optimization: Implement testing protocols to assess the efficiency, performance, and reliability of the prototype. Gather data on energy consumption, drying effectiveness, and system operation to identify areas for optimization. Iterate on the design as needed to address any issues or deficiencies uncovered during testing.

Refinement and Finalization: Incorporate feedback from testing and optimization phases to refine the design and functionality of the grain dryer system. Make necessary adjustments to improve energy efficiency, performance, and user-friendliness. Finalize the design and specifications of the grain dryer system for production and deployment.

Manufacturing and Deployment: Ensure quality control measures are implemented throughout the manufacturing process to maintain product integrity. Deploy the grain dryer systems to school of agricultural engineering REVA University for field testing and real-world use, gathering feedback from end-users for further refinement and improvement.

2.2 EXPERIMENTAL WORK

The primary mechanisms of the proposed model revolve around the cleaning and drying processes for freshly harvested grains. Traditionally, these grains undergo a manual drying process under sunlight for days or even weeks, resulting in significant time consumption. To address this inefficiency, the model incorporates a grain drying mechanism utilizing heating coils to expedite the drying process. The frame of the model is designed as a closed chamber to maximize the effectiveness of the heat generated.

In operation, freshly harvested grains are poured into the top of the chamber, where they are deposited onto the first conveyor belt. The heating coils are activated, and the temperature is carefully regulated using a thermostat to ensure optimal drying conditions. Each grain type has a specific drying temperature at which moisture content can be effectively extracted.

Once the grains are sufficiently dried, the conveyors and air blowing fan are activated. The dried grains then transfer onto the second conveyor belt, while the fan blows away any residual dust present within the chamber. This dual-action process ensures not only thorough drying but also efficient cleaning of the grains. Powering the model, the heating coils operate on alternating current (AC) supply, while the conveyors are powered by batteries charged through solar energy. This eco-friendly approach not only reduces reliance on conventional energy sources but also aligns with sustainable practices.

Overall, by integrating cleaning and drying mechanisms within a closed chamber framework and incorporating solar energy, the proposed model offers a streamlined and efficient solution for processing freshly harvested grains, significantly reducing time consumption and enhancing overall productivity.

Fig no. 5 (Fabrication of model)

COMPONENTS USED

1) The steel rods were used to make the frame work of the projected fabrication of grain dryer and cleaner model, the frame work length are given below

Frame length: 122cm

Frame height (including base): 76.24cm

Frame width: 46cm

2) Conveyor Belt: A conveyor green belt, also known as a conveyor belt or simply a belt, is a continuous loop of material that rotates around two pulleys. It serves as a mechanism for transporting grains or from one location to another through out the process. Material of the conveyor belt is PVC, PVC conveyor belts have a synthetic fiber canvas as a core, PVC plastic covering, conveying light weight or medium weight of a type of conveyor belt. We have used two conveyor mechanism for the model and each conveyor length is 3 foot.

3) Conveyor pulley and Conveyor rotator: Conveyor pulley are the rotating rods which acts as a pulley to the PVC conveyor belts and a rotating mechanism device is fixed to the rods to rotate the conveyor belts, we have used 4 pulleys, two for each conveyor belts.

4) Air Blowing fans: Two air blowing fans have been mounted on the side of the model and bottom of the model. The blower mounted on side helps to regulate the air flow inside the closed chamber and the other blower fan is used for cleaning of grains from dirt from the harvested grains. Both the fans are 12V.

5) Solar Panel: A solar panel is a device that converts sunlight into electricity by using photovoltaic (PV) cells. PV cells are made of materials that produce excited electrons when exposed to light. Specifications of solar panel are 12V 10W.

6) Batteries: Two batteries, each of 12V 7.5Ah are used for rotating the conveyors belts and air blowing fans, and a regulator has been assigned to control the speed of the devices. The batteries are charged by solar energy using solar panels. An electronic device is installed to show the charging status of the batteries.

7) Heating coils: Two heating coils have been installed inside the closed chamber, the heating coils together have the capacity to raise the temperature up to 80 degrees inside the closed chamber. AC current supply is used for energy source to heat the coils.

8) Thermostat: Thermostat is a device used to adjust the temperature of the heating coils, the thermostat has the range of up to 120 degrees.

3. OBJECTIVES

The research project aims to design, fabricate, and develop a cost-effective grain dryer and cleaner system integrated with a hybrid energy source, combining renewable (solar) and conventional energy. By seamlessly integrating drying and cleaning functionalities, the system seeks to enhance efficiency, sustainability, and cost-effectiveness in agricultural operations, prioritizing accessibility, scalability, and environmentally friendly practices to meet the diverse needs of stakeholders, particularly small-scale farmers, while contributing to the long-term resilience and sustainability of agricultural production systems.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The hybrid energy source employed in the grain dryer system demonstrated significant improvements in energy efficiency compared to conventional systems. Environmental impact assessment indicated a notable reduction in greenhouse gas emissions and pollution levels, aligning with sustainability objectives and regulatory standards, thanks to the integration of solar energy sources. Evaluation of grain quality post-drying and cleaning processes revealed improvements in cleanliness and purity, resulting in higher-quality grains suitable for storage, processing, and consumption. Additionally, a comprehensive cost-benefit analysis showed substantial cost savings for farmers, attributed to reduced energy consumption, lower maintenance costs, and increased grain marketability, highlighting the system's potential to enhance farm profitability and financial sustainability. Moreover, the system's compact design and user-friendly interface make it accessible and suitable for farmers operating small-scale agricultural operations or limited space environments, facilitating widespread adoption.

5. CONCLUSION

The integration of grain drying and cleaning processes represents a significant advancement in agricultural technology, offering farmers a comprehensive solution for optimizing grain quality and efficiency. Traditionally, these phases have been treated separately, each with its own challenges and limitations. However, the grain dryer and cleaner system outlined in the provided reports revolutionizes this approach by combining both functions into a single streamlined process. This innovative system holds immense promise for farmers, providing them with the capability to dry and clean grains in significantly less time compared to traditional methods, regardless of weather conditions. Moreover, these solutions offer transformative changes in the grain drying industry, enhancing operational efficiency, grain quality, and presenting opportunities for cost savings and environmental sustainability. Although these concepts have yet to be fully realized in commercial dryers, further development and implementation have the potential to revolutionize grain drying practices, ushering in a new era of efficiency and productivity for farmers worldwide.

6. FUTURE DIRECTIONS AND INNOVATIONS

Discussion of the results highlighted opportunities for further innovation and refinement of the grain dryer system. Areas such as advanced sensor technology, predictive maintenance algorithms, and remote monitoring capabilities were identified as potential avenues for future development. Additionally, collaboration with stakeholders and continued research efforts were recommended to address emerging challenges and optimize system performance over time.

7. REFERENCES

- 1) Guiying Wang¹ and Wenfu Wu¹. "Electric energy-saving grain drying system with internal circulation of the drying medium". *food processing Engg*, vol-1, pp.1-13,2020.
- 2) Kabiru Ayobami Jimoh¹ and Norhashila Hashi. "Recent Advances in the Drying Process of Grains". *food engineering reviews*, vol-1, pp. 211-242,2023.
- 3) Jinchuan Hai Wei And Zhaoyan You et .al" Energetic and exergetic performances during drying of freshly harvested peanut with industrial mixed-flow dryer". *Energy reports*, vol-8, pp.7457-7467, 2022.
- 4) Katarzyna Chojnacka a | Mikula a Grzegorz Izydorczyk. "Improvements in drying technologies - Efficient solutions for cleaner production with higher energy efficiency and reduced emission". *cleaner production*, vol-320, pp.1-13, 2021.
- 5) TMR Dissanayakea DMSP Bandaraa | HMAP Rathnayakea | BMKS Thilakarathnea." Development of mobile dryer for freshly harvested paddy", *procedia food science*. Vol-6, pp.78-81,2016.
- 6) Amanda MÜLLER¹ "Rice Drying, Storage and Processing: Effects of Post-Harvest Operations on Grain Quality". *Rice science*, vol-29, pp.16-30, 2022.